

IMPACT OF YOGACHARA ON TRANSMISSION DYNAMICS OF INFECTIOUS DISEASE: SIQS MODEL ANALYSIS AT SATURATED INCIDENCE RATE

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Abstract

Communicable diseases are major health problems and affect the whole economy of the nation. So, it should become the prime agenda of developed and developing countries to prevent them. It seems necessary to educate people about disease transmission dynamics and to develop a new prevention strategy. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the effects of prevention strategies like Yogachara with quarantine. Yogachara (ahar, Vihar, achar and Vichar) boosts people psychologically and makes them aware of the disease. Mathematical epidemiology describes all the possible risk factors of communicable diseases, treatment modalities, human health policies and new opportunities for the planning, prevention and treatment of the diseases. Yogachara provides public health information as well as maintains the physical fitness of practitioners improves the whole metabolic system of the human body and helps to achieve the physical, mental, social and spiritual well-being of the practitioners. Motivated by the Eastern philosophy of Yoga, an SIQS mathematical model has been developed which contains three governing ordinary differential equations to describe the transmission dynamics of communicable disease. These equations were analyzed by using mathematical techniques. The next-generation matrix method is used to calculate the reproduction number and sensitivity analysis of parameters indicates that the reproduction number decreases with increased preventive measures like Yogachara. Local and global stability analysis at disease-free and endemic equilibria are calculated. Our results highlight that the theory-based and data-based Yogachara effect terms have almost the same result. Numerical simulations suggest that Yogachara has a positive influence in controlling disease dynamics. It reduces size in susceptibility and infectivity.

Keywords: Transmission Dynamics, Pranayama, Immunity Power, Epidemic Equilibrium.

1. INTRODUCTION

The most commonly used effective methods to control the spread of disease are vaccination, treatment, awareness, and quarantine. To reduce transmission dynamics of infectious disease, one intervention procedure is to isolate some infective individuals. In Eastern philosophy, "quarantine" can be understood metaphorically as a practice or period of separation for purification, reflection, and growth, rather than its literal modern use related to disease control. Quarantine can be seen as a period of non-action, allowing one to align with natural rhythms and

cycles. In Eastern philosophy, quarantine is regarded as purification and self-discovery or Sadhana (Spiritual Practice). It also involves periods of isolation for meditation, fasting, or prayer, reflecting the idea of quarantining oneself to attain higher spiritual insight [10, 12]. In Eastern philosophy, the metaphorical idea of quarantine aligns with the themes of isolation for purification, reflection, and growth. Whether it is through physical isolation in retreats, ethical self-cultivation, or aligning oneself with natural rhythms, the concept mirrors the modern notion of quarantine as a necessary separation for healing and renewal [5, 11, 19, 21].

Generally, quarantine is a protective measure involving restricting movement and interaction to prevent the spread of contagious diseases. It has historical roots in maritime practices and has evolved into a critical component of modern public health strategies. The purpose of this article is to use Yogachara along with quarantine.

Quarantines can last as long as health personnel or authorities deem necessary to prevent the spread of an epidemic. In quarantine, we forcefully or voluntarily isolate some infective individuals from the infective class. It implies the isolation of large groups of people (communities, cities, countries) and requires the closure or restriction of activities that generate crowds (shopping centres, restaurants, public events, etc.). In general, the duration and terms of this type of quarantine are decided by the local power following recommendations from health personnel, and measures such as total or partial restriction of movement in a given territory, allowing commercial activity only in essential items like food and health, totally or partially limit public transport, use of public force to enforce the terms of the quarantine.

In the SIQS model infectious do not confer immunity, some of the susceptible become infected and then some infectives remain in the infectious class I for their whole infectious period before they return to the susceptible class S , while other infective individuals are transferred into a quarantine class Q [14, 24]. Some quarantine models on disease transmission were formulated with different reaction incidence rates and the effect of quarantine was studied. The incidence in an epidemic model is the rate at which susceptible becomes infectious. Some incidence rates such as bilinear, nonlinear, standard, saturated, non-monotone etc. have been defined and studied by different authors in epidemic models and presented a thorough qualitative analysis of the models [2, 16, 28]. Hethcote et al. [6, 27] analyzed the effect of quarantine in some epidemic models with simple mass action, standard and quarantine-adjusted incidence rates. Motivated from the work of [6, 7, 27], the $SIQS$ epidemic model is considered with quarantine and saturated incidence rate given by $g(S, I) = \frac{\beta SI}{1 + \alpha S}$. This incidence rate is more suitable for real-world than other incidence rates and is often used in epidemiology when the population is saturated with infectives [4, 22, 23]. Different authors analyzed the epidemic model with a saturated incidence rate and treatment. Various kinds of endemic equilibria and disease-free equilibrium states were analyzed with different stability and qualitative theory [1, 3, 9, 15, 17, 18]. We formulate the $SIQS$ model with Yogachara (Ahara, Vihara, Achara, and Vichara) at a saturated incident rate. First, we obtained the disease-free and endemic equilibrium and then discussed the stability at these equilibrium points. Finally, the numerical simulations are carried out to support the theoretical analysis.

2. MODEL FORMULATION

The model is given by following non-linear ordinary differentiable equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dS}{dt} &= b - \frac{\beta SI}{1+\alpha S} - \mu S + \gamma I + \theta Q \\ \frac{dI}{dt} &= \frac{\beta SI}{1+\alpha S} - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d)I \\ \frac{dQ}{dt} &= \lambda I - (\theta + \mu + d)Q. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The variables and parameters used in these equations are defined in the following table. All above parameters $b, \beta, \mu, \lambda, d, \theta, \gamma, \alpha$ are positive constants.

Table 1: Variables and Parameters used in the model

Variables/Parameters	Definitions
b	Recruitment rate (including births and immigrations) of susceptible individuals,
μ	Per capita natural death rate,
β	The average number of adequate contacts (sufficient for transmission) of a person per unit of time,
λ	The rate constant for individuals leaving the infective compartment I for the quarantine compartment Q,
d	Disease-related death rate constant in compartments I and Q,
γ	The rate at which individuals recover and return to susceptible compartment S from compartment I,
θ	The rate at which individuals recover and return to susceptible compartment S from compartment Q,
α	Parameter measures Yogachara prevention taken by susceptible populations for epidemic control.

Total population size, $N = S + I + Q$, that is, $N' = S' + I' + Q'$.

Figure 1: The general transfer diagram for the SIQS model

$$N' = b - \mu N - d(I + Q)$$

In absence of disease related death, $N' = b - \mu N$. This gives $N = \frac{b}{\mu} + e^{-\mu t}(N_0 - \frac{b}{\mu})$.

As $t \rightarrow \infty, N \rightarrow \frac{b}{\mu}$, that is population size approaches to carrying capacity $\frac{b}{\mu}$. It follows that solution of the model (1) exists in the positive region defined by $\Omega = \{(S, I, Q) \in R_3^+ : S, I, Q \geq 0, S + I + Q \leq \frac{b}{\mu}\}$.

3. EQUILIBRIUM STATES AND QUARANTINE REPRODUCTION NUMBER

For the equilibrium point of system (1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} b - \frac{\beta SI}{1+\alpha S} - \mu S + \gamma I + \theta Q &= 0 \\ \frac{\beta SI}{1+\alpha S} - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d)I &= 0 \\ \lambda I - (\theta + \mu + d)Q &= 0. \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

The system (2) always has the disease-free equilibrium point $E_0 \left(\frac{b}{\mu}, 0, 0 \right)$

We define the threshold R_q as the average number of secondary infections produced when one primarily infected person is entered into a fully susceptible population [20]. The number R_q is called the quarantine reproduction number. Here we are using the term ‘quarantine reproduction number’ for the threshold, because in the model the quarantine process is used to control the disease. It is one of the most useful parameters which find out that an infection will be eliminated or survives in the population. We shall find the expression for R_q by using a method explained in [20].

Let $X = (S, I, Q)$, then we have $X' = \mathcal{F} - \mathcal{V}$,

Where,

$$\mathcal{F} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{\beta SI}{1+\alpha S} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

And

$$\mathcal{V} = \begin{bmatrix} -b + \frac{\beta SI}{1+\alpha S} + \mu S - \gamma I - \theta Q \\ (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d)I \\ -\lambda I + (\theta + \mu + d)Q \end{bmatrix}$$

At disease-free equilibrium $\left(\frac{b}{\mu}, 0, 0 \right)$, variation matrices of F and V are given by

$$F_0 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\beta b}{\mu+\alpha b} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

And

$$V_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \mu & \frac{\beta b}{\mu+\alpha b} - \gamma & -\theta \\ 0 & \gamma + \lambda + \mu + d & 0 \\ 0 & -\lambda & \theta + \mu + d \end{bmatrix}$$

The next generation matrix for this model 1 is

$$F_0 V_0^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\beta b}{(\mu+\alpha b)(\gamma+\lambda+\mu+d)} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The spectral radius of the matrix gives R_q , that is,

$$R_q = \frac{\beta b}{(\mu + \alpha b)(\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d)}$$

We obtain a unique positive equilibrium known as endemic equilibrium point $E^* = (S^*, I^*, Q^*)$ of the system (1) in Ω by solving 2 when $R_q > 1$

$$\begin{aligned} S^* &= \frac{b}{\alpha b(R_q - 1) + \mu R_q} \\ I^* &= \frac{b(\theta + \mu + d)(b\alpha + \mu)[R_q - 1]}{(\mu + \lambda)(\theta + \mu + \lambda + d)[\alpha b(R_q - 1) + \mu R_q]} \\ Q^* &= \frac{\lambda I^*}{\theta + \mu + d} \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Also,

$$N^* = S^* + I^* + Q^* = \frac{bd}{(\mu + d)[\alpha b(R_q - 1) + \mu R_q]} + \frac{b}{\mu + d}$$

It is clear that when the disease-related death rate constant $d = 0$, the total population N^* at the endemic equilibrium E^* approaches to the disease-free carrying capacity $\frac{b}{\mu}$.

4. STABILITY ANALYSIS

In this section, we will establish local and global stability analysis of the model 1.

4.1 Local Stability Analysis

Theorem 5.1. *If $R_q < 1$, then the disease-free equilibrium E_0 of the system 1 is locally asymptotically stable. If $R_q > 1$, then the equilibrium E_0 is unstable.*

Proof: Consider

$$M_1 = b - \frac{\beta SI}{1 + \alpha S} - \mu S + \gamma I + \theta Q$$

$$M_2 = \frac{\beta SI}{1 + \alpha S} - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d)I$$

$$M_3 = \lambda I - (\theta + \mu + d)Q$$

The Variation matrix of system 1 is

$$V(X) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial M_1}{\partial S} & \frac{\partial M_1}{\partial I} & \frac{\partial M_1}{\partial Q} \\ \frac{\partial M_2}{\partial S} & \frac{\partial M_2}{\partial I} & \frac{\partial M_2}{\partial Q} \\ \frac{\partial M_3}{\partial S} & \frac{\partial M_3}{\partial I} & \frac{\partial M_3}{\partial Q} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$V(X) = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\beta I}{(1 + \alpha S)^2} - \mu & \frac{-\beta S}{1 + \alpha S} + \gamma & \theta \\ \frac{\beta I}{(1 + \alpha S)^2} & \frac{\beta S}{1 + \alpha S} - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d) & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & -(\theta + \mu + d) \end{bmatrix}$$

Variation matrix at disease free equilibrium $E_0 = (\frac{b}{\mu}, 0, 0)$ is given by

$$V(E_0) = \begin{bmatrix} -\mu & \frac{-\beta}{\mu+\alpha b} + \gamma & \theta \\ 0 & \frac{\beta}{\mu+\alpha b} - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d) & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & -(\theta + \mu + d) \end{bmatrix}$$

The characteristic polynomial of $V(E_0)$ is given by

$$|V(E_0) - IK| = 0$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\mu - K & \frac{-\beta}{\mu + \alpha b} + \gamma & \theta \\ 0 & \frac{\beta}{\mu + \alpha b} - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d) - K & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & -(\theta + \mu + d) - K \end{bmatrix} = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (\mu + K)(\theta + \mu + d) + K[(K + (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d) - \frac{\beta}{\mu + \alpha b})] = 0$$

Clearly, two Eigen values are negative and third will also be negative if $\frac{\beta}{\mu + \alpha b} < (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d)$

$$\text{i.e. } R_q < 1$$

Hence, the disease-free equilibrium E_0 is locally asymptotically stable if $R_q < 1$ and unstable if

$$R_q > 1$$

Theorem 5.2. The endemic equilibrium (EE) is locally asymptotically stable for $R_q > 1$

Proof: At endemic equilibrium $E^* = (S^*, I^*, Q^*)$, the variation matrix

$$V(E^*) = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\beta I^*}{(1+\alpha S^*)^2} - \mu & \frac{-\beta S^*}{1+\alpha S^*} + \gamma & \theta \\ \frac{\beta I^*}{(1+\alpha S^*)^2} & \frac{\beta S^*}{1+\alpha S^*} - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d) & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & -(\theta + \mu + d) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$V(E^*) = \begin{bmatrix} -A - \mu & -B + \gamma & \theta \\ A & B - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d) & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & -(\theta + \mu + d) \end{bmatrix}$$

Where, $A = \frac{\beta I^*}{(1+\alpha S^*)^2}$, $B = \frac{\beta S^*}{1+\alpha S^*}$

The characteristic polynomial of $V(E^*)$ is given by

$$|V(E^*) - KI| = \begin{bmatrix} -A - \mu - K & -B + \gamma & \theta \\ A & B - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d) - K & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & -(\theta + \mu + d) - K \end{bmatrix} = 0$$

that is,

$$(K + A + \mu)(K + (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d) - B)(K + \theta + \mu + d) + A[(B - \gamma)(K + \theta + \mu + d - \theta\lambda)] = 0$$

Putting $D = \gamma + \lambda + \mu + d$, $C = \theta + \mu + d$ and $M = A + \mu$ and solving,

we get

$$K_3 + a_1K_2 + a_2K + a_3 = 0$$

Where,

$$a_1 = M + C + D - B$$

$$= C + D + \mu + (A - B)$$

$$a_2 = MC + (M + C)(D - B) + A(B - \gamma)$$

$$= \mu(C + D) + CD + A(d + \lambda) + (A - B)(C + d) a_3 = MC(D - B) - A\theta\lambda + AC(B - \gamma)$$

$$= (A - B)\mu C + A[dC + \lambda(\mu + d)] + \mu CD$$

$$a_1a_2 - a_3 = (C + D)[\mu(\mu + C + D) + CD] + (A - B)[(\mu + C)(\mu + C + 2D) + A(d + \lambda)] + (A - B)^2(\mu + C) + A[\theta\lambda + (d + \lambda)(\mu + D)]$$

Clearly, $a_1, a_2, a_3 > 0$, and $a_1a_2 - a_3 > 0$ provided $(A - B) > 0$.

Hence by Routh-Hurwitz criteria for the endemic equilibrium E^* is locally asymptotically stable if $R_q > 1$.

Figure 2: This figure shows the Stability of the system.

4.2 Global Stability Analysis

We use the Lyapunov global asymptotic stability theorem to test the global stability of the system [25, 26].

Theorem 5.3. Consider a nonlinear system $x' = f(x)$, and suppose there exists a function $L: R_n \rightarrow R$

Such that

- L is positive definite
- $L'(z) < 0$ for all $z \neq 0$ and $L'(0) = 0$

Then, every trajectory of $x' = f(x)$ converges to zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$ (i.e., the system is globally asymptotically stable) [13]

Theorem 5.4.

(a) If $R_q < 1$, then the disease-free equilibrium E_0 of the system (1) is globally asymptotically stable in the region Ω

b) If $R_q > 1$ and $d = 0$ (i.e. there are no disease-related deaths), then the endemic equilibrium

E^* is globally asymptotically stable in the region $\Omega - (S, I, Q) : I = 0$.

Proof: First, we prove the global stability at the disease-free equilibrium E_0 when $R_q > 1$. Consider a Lyapunov function $L = I$. Then the Lyapunov derivative will be

$$L' = I'$$

$$L' = \left[\frac{\beta S}{1+\alpha S} - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d) \right] I^*$$

$$L' \leq \left[\frac{\beta b}{\mu+\alpha b} \left(1 - \frac{1}{R_q} \right) \right] I^*$$

Since $S \leq \frac{\beta b}{\mu+\alpha b}$

Thus, if $R_q < 1$, then $L' \leq 0$ and also $L' = 0$ if and only if $S = \frac{b}{\mu}$, $I = 0$ and $Q = 0$.

Therefore, $\{E_0\}$ is the largest positive invariant set in $\{(S, I, Q) \in \Omega : L' = 0\}$, where $E_0 = \left(\frac{b}{\mu+\alpha b}, 0, 0 \right)$ is disease free equilibrium. Thus, by Lyapunov's invariant principle, E_0 is globally asymptotically stable in Ω . To prove the global stability of E^* when $R_q > 1$ and $d = 0$ (i.e. there are no disease-related deaths), we have $N' = b - \mu N$. This gives $N \rightarrow \frac{b}{\mu}$. In this case the limit system of (1) is given by

$$N' = 0$$

$$I' = \left[\frac{\left(\frac{b}{\mu} - I - Q \right)}{1+\alpha \left(\frac{b}{\mu} - I - Q \right)} - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu) \right] I \tag{4}$$

$$Q' = \lambda I - (\theta + \mu)Q$$

Now, we discuss in the first quadrant of $IQ - Plane$. Using Dulac's criteria with multipliers $D_1 = \frac{1}{I}$,

Let $F_1 = \left[\frac{\beta \left(\frac{b}{\mu} - I - Q \right)}{1+\alpha \left(\frac{b}{\mu} - I - Q \right)} - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu) \right] I$, $F_2 = \lambda I - (\theta + \mu)Q$

Then, $D_1 F_1 = \left[\frac{\beta \left(\frac{b}{\mu} - I - Q \right)}{1+\alpha \left(\frac{b}{\mu} - I - Q \right)} - (\gamma + \lambda + \mu) \right]$ and $D_1 F_2 = \lambda I - (\theta + \mu) \frac{Q}{I}$

We have $\frac{\partial(D_1 F_1)}{\partial I} + \frac{\partial(D_1 F_2)}{\partial(Q)} = - \frac{\beta}{\left[1+\alpha \left(\frac{b}{\mu} - I - Q \right) \right]^2} - \frac{\theta+\mu}{I} < 0$

Thus, there is no limit cycle i.e. no periodic solutions exist in the region. Hence by Poincare-Bendixson theory [8], endemic equilibrium E^* is globally asymptotically stable in the region $\Omega - \{(S, I, Q) : I = 0\}$ for the limit system 2 and hence for the original system 1.

5. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Sensitivity Analysis

In order to get sensitivity analysis, we use following parametric values.

Table 2: Parametric values used in the system 1

Parameter	Value	Reference
α	[0.4-1]	Assumed
β	[0.01-0.8]	[7]
λ	[0.1-0.5]	[7]
b	[8 - 10]	[7]
γ	[0.1 - 0.5]	[7]
d	[0 - 0.3]	[7]
μ	[0-0.2]	[7]
θ	[0.1 - 0.2]	[7]

Sensitivity index of R_q to the parameter γ_i for parameter values are given in the table

Table 3: Sensitivity of R_q for given parametric values

Parameter (γ_i)	Sensitivity index of R_q w.r.t. parameter γ_i	Numerical Value
β	1	1
λ	$\frac{-\lambda}{\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d}$	-0.5
α	$\frac{-\alpha b}{\mu + \alpha b}$	-0.93
γ	$-\frac{\gamma}{(\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d)}$	-0.33
B	1	1
μ	$-\frac{\beta b(\alpha b + \gamma + \lambda + 2\mu = d)}{(\mu + \alpha b)^2(\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d)^2}$	-1.680
D	$-\frac{d}{(\gamma + \lambda + \mu + d)}$	-0.22

5.2 Numerical Simulations

We have carried out the global analysis of an SIQS model and observed that the basic quarantine reproduction number R_q plays an important role in controlling the disease. Our main results show that if $R_q < 1$, the disease-free equilibrium is globally stable and if $R_q > 1$, then the endemic equilibrium exists and is globally stable. Besides this analytical study, we provide some numerical solutions as under:

5.3 Disease-Free Equilibrium

Choosing parameters $b = 10, \mu = 0.15, \beta = 0.02, \gamma = 0.6, \alpha = 1, \lambda = 0.4, d = 0.25, \theta = 0.25, (S(0), I(0), Q(0)) = (50, 20, 10)$ (from table 2) gives $R_q < 1$. In this case, $S(t)$ approaches its steady state value while $I(t)$ and $Q(t)$ approach to zero as time goes to infinity, the disease disappears and dies out as shown in figures 4 and 5.

5.4 Endemic Equilibrium

Choosing the parameters as $b = 10, \mu = 0.1, \beta = 0.6, \gamma = 0.3, \alpha = 0.5, \lambda = 0.4, d = 0, \theta = 0.1, (S(0), I(0), Q(0)) = (50, 20, 10)$ (from table (2)) gives $R_q > 1$ and in this case all the components $S(t), I(t)$ and $Q(t)$ approaches to their steady-state values as time goes to infinity, the disease becomes endemic as shown in figures 6,

and 7. The quarantine process with Yogachara is one of the methods for reducing the average infectious period by isolating some infectives, so that they do not transmit the infection. In the above model with quarantine, we can see that the effective infectious period $\frac{1}{\gamma+\mu+\lambda+d}$ and R_q decreases as the quarantine rate constant increases. Since the mean residence time in the quarantine class Q is $\frac{1}{\theta}$ and the expression for R_q is independent of parameter θ , it shows that the assumption of quarantine models that the people in the quarantine class Q do not infect others and people are not infectious when they move out of the quarantine class, is acceptable. Also, it is clear from the expressions of R_q that it depends on α and is decreases as α increases, it indicates that the spread of diseases decreases as the Yogachhara (awareness or Yoga Pranayama) rate increases as shown in figures 6 and 7. The relation of quarantine reproduction with parameters is illustrated in figure 3. Sensitivity analysis also shows that quarantine reproduction decreases as Yogachara increases.

Figure 3: Sensitivity Indices of the Quarantine Reproduction number to the parameter values

Figure 4: Disease die out when quarantine rate and Yogachara (awareness) increases ($R_q < 1$)

Figure 5: Disease-free equilibrium when $R_q < 1$.

Figure 6: Disease Steady State (Endemic Equilibrium) when $R_q > 1$

Figure 7: Endemic Equilibrium when $R_q > 1$ (Disease remains in the population)

6. CONCLUSION

In this article, an S/QS epidemic model with quarantine and Yogachara strategy is analyzed at saturated incidence rate. The threshold quantity (quarantine reproduction number) R_q is obtained which analyzes the effect of the quarantine (Yogachara) and consequences of the disease. If R_q is less than 1, then the disease-free equilibrium exists and is globally stable, that is, the disease dies out as shown in figures 4, and 5. If R_q is greater than 1, then there exists a unique positive equilibrium condition and is globally stable, that is, the disease becomes endemic. In this model, we can see that the effective infectious period and R_q both decrease as the quarantine rate λ increases. It means that as fast as the quarantine of infectious people takes place, the disease tends to extinction. Since the mean

residence time in the quarantine class Q is $\frac{1}{\theta}$ and the expression for R_q is independent of parameter θ , it shows that the assumption of the quarantine model that the people in the quarantine class Q do not infect others and people are not infectious when they move out of the quarantine class, is acceptable. In addition, it is obvious from the expressions of R_q that it depends on α and is decreases as α increases. It shows that the spread of disease decreases as the psychological protective measures like Yogachara (Pranayama, Yoga awareness) for the infective increases. Besides this analytical study, we provide some numerical solutions which support the analytical study. Graphs shown in figures 4, 5, 6 and 7 verify these results. These results show that when quarantine rate and Yogachara (psychological protective measures or awareness) increase, $S(t)$ approaches to its steady state value, $I(t)$ approaches to zero as time goes to infinity. Consequently, $Q(t)$ also approaches to zero, disease disappears and dies out as shown in figures 3 to 7.

Further Improvement

In this paper, we are trying to explore the impact of Yogachara along with quarantine to the transmission of infection diseases. The model (1) is an SIQS model at saturated incident rate and the purpose of analyzing the impact of Yogachara on the spreading of the disease. In the model, we have used a transmission rate $\frac{\beta}{1+\alpha S}I$. for further study, it would be ideal to consider more realistic transmission rates to reflect the impact of Yoga Pranayama or awareness on disease transmission dynamics. Yet, the analysis of such new models can be mathematically more challenging due to the higher dimension of the models and non-linearity of the incidence function.

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